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FOREST DRAGON-3: DECADAL TRENDS OF NORTHEASTERN FORESTS IN CHINA FROM EARTH OBSERVATION SYNERGY

C. Schullius¹, J. Balling¹, P. Schratz¹, C. Thiel¹, M. Santoro², U. Wegmuller², Z. Li³, and P. Yong³

¹Department of Earth Observation, Friedrich-Schiller-University, Grietgasse 6, D-07743 Jena, Germany
Email: c.schullius@uni-jena.de, johannes.balling@uni-jena.de, patrick.schratz@uni-jena.de, christian.thiel@uni-jena.de

²Gamma Remote Sensing, Worbstrasse 225, CH-3073 Gümligen, Switzerland
Email: santoro@gamma-rs.ch, wegmuller@gamma-rs.ch

³Research Institute of Forest Resource Information Techniques, Chinese Academy of Forestry, Wanshoushan Hou, Haidian, 1000091 Beijing, China
Email: lizy@caf.ac.cn, pangy@ifrit.ac.cn

ABSTRACT

In Forest DRAGON 3, synergy of Earth Observation products to derive information of decadal trends of forest in northeast China was investigated. Following up the results of Forest-DRAGON 1 and 2, Growing Stock Volume (GSV) products from different years were investigated to derive information on vegetational in northeast China. The BIOMASAR maps of 2005 and 2010, produced within the previous DRAGON projects, set the base for all analyses. We took a closer look at scale problems regarding GSV derivation, which are introduced by differing landcover within one pixel, to investigate differences throughout pixel classes with varying landcover class percentages. We developed an approach to select pixels containing forest only with the aim of undertaking a detailed analysis on retrieved GSV values for such pixels for the years 2005 and 2010. Using existing land cover products at different scales, the plausibility of changes in the BIOMASAR maps were checked.

Key words: CCI Landcover; Biomass; Growing Stock Volume, BIOMASAR, MODIS Landcover, Globeland30.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades biomass estimation utilizing remote sensing data has moved into the center of attention of interdisciplinary research for the quantification and validation of complex carbon storage [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. The latter is the most complex part of the carbon cycle and has therefore a huge impact on analysis of the global climate change [7].

For this purpose several methods have been developed for estimating biomass based on Light Detection And Rang-

ing (LiDAR)- [1], optical- [2] or Radio Detection And Ranging (RADAR) remote sensing data [3, 5, 4, 6].

To tackle the issue of biomass estimation, Forest DRAGON's objective is to monitor forest ecosystems in China using remote sensing data [8]. The northeast and Southeast areas of China possess some of the most important wood supplies in China and underwent drastic changes in the recent past [9]. Therefore Forest DRAGON 1 & 2 GSV maps based on ERS-1/2 data with a spatial resolution of 50 m were produced for 1995 and 1998 in the northeast and Southeast of China [9, 10]. Hereby GSV refers to the stem/bore volume of living trees for all living species, including bark and excluding branches and stumps [5]. These maps marked the first synergistic product using optical and radar based remote sensing data for biomass estimation during the Forest DRAGON project [3]. During Forest DRAGON 2, the more sophisticated BIOMASAR algorithm [5], which uses hypertextural stacks of ENVISAT's Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR) imagery and Moderate-resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Vegetation Continuous Fields (VCF) data for GSV estimation, was used to produce GSV maps for 2005 and 2010 of northeast China [8]. This data was used to generate a GSV change map from 2005 to 2010 for northeast China based on a qualitative validation approach [8]. Forest DRAGON 3 had the objective to produce validated forest GSV maps for 2005 and 2010, and investigate scaling effects in mapping forest GSV based on these maps. To account for scaling effects and a validation approach, a pure- and mixed pixel analysis for forest areas based on the BIOMASAR GSV maps of 2005 and 2010 was carried out to investigate the behaviour of the BIOMASAR algorithm for pure and mixed forest pixel (section 3). Moreover, a plausibility check using various existing remote sensing products was carried out for a cross-comparison estimating the reliability of the produced BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010 for northeast China (see subsection 3.3).

2. DATA AND STUDY AREA

For the investigation of pure- and mixed forest pixel within the BIOMASAR GSV maps of 2005 & 2010, various remote sensing products were used. The BIOMASAR products itself feature a spatial resolution of 1 km and provide GSV estimations in m^3/ha . The BIOMASAR algorithm uses backscatter information on hypertemporal ASAR stacks to calculate GSV [5]. The algorithm uses MODIS VCF information to separate between 'unvegetated' and 'dense forest' areas. According to [5], retrieved GSV values are only valid for forest pixels. However, GSV retrievals are provided for all pixels in the BIOMASAR products. Product validation showed a relative Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between 34.2% and 48.1% depending on biome and surface conditions [5].

Table 1. Specifications of remote sensing products used within the 'Pure Pixel Analysis', 'Mixed Pixel Analysis' and 'Plausibility Check'

Product	Year	Product type	Spatial resolution
BIOMASAR GSV	2005 & 2010	GSV map	1km
CCI LC	2005 & 2010	Land Cover	300m
MODIS LC	2005 - 2010	Land Cover	500m
GlobeLand	2010	Land Cover	30m
PALSAR Forest/Non-forest	2009	Forest/Non-forest map	25m
MODIS NDVI	2005 - 2010	Vegetation product	1km
MODIS VCF	2005 - 2010	Vegetation product	250m
MODIS Burned Area	2005 - 2010	Fire product	500m
Landsat based Burned Area	2005 - 2010	Fire product	30m

Three available Landcover (LC) products were utilized to distinguish between 'Pure Forest' and 'Mixed Forest' (see Table 1), namely CCI Landcover [11], MODIS Landcover [12] and 'GlobeLand30m' [13]. The Climate Change Initiative (CCI) LC product was the most important one for the analysis as it showed the highest consistency throughout the years and has a better spatial resolution than MODIS LC (300 m vs. 500 m). It was produced by European Space Agency (ESA) CCI team for the years 2000, 2005 and 2010 [11]. Its classification algorithm is based on MERIS- and SPOT vegetation time series data to meet the condition of the widely known, hierarchical Land Cover Classification System (LCCS). The 'GlobeLand30m' product was only available for the year 2010. MODIS LC, which features a spatial resolution of 500 m [12], is based on composited, recurring 8-day MODIS observations, normalized BRDF-adjusted reflectance data and MODIS land surface temperature data [12]. While CCI LC relies on LCCS, MODIS LC uses its own classification scheme [12]. Within the analyses all yearly LC classification products from 2005 until 2010 were used [12]. Additionally, the LC product 'GlobeLand30m' was used, which is based on Landsat images from 2009 - 2011 and multispectral images of HJ-1 [13] and features a spatial resolution of 30 m with an overall accuracy of 83,5% [13]. Besides these LC products, the Advanced Land Observation Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) Forest/Non-Forest map with a spatial resolution of 25 m was used [14]. For the acquisition of this product, forest areas were classi-

Figure 1. Study area & terrain heights

fied based using HV-polarization information of ALOS PALSAR. This Forest/Non-Forest map features an overall accuracy of 84% [14]. Moreover, monthly data of the vegetation products MODIS Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), MODIS VCF and the fire product MODIS burned area from 2005 - 2010 with 1 km, 250 m and 500 m spatial resolution respectively was available which was mainly used for the 'Plausibility Check' (see subsection 3.3). [15, 16, 17]. Last, the fire product created within the 'Forest Fires & Emissions' DRAGON 3 project was utilized. It was derived by manually digitizing forest fires via Landsat data from 2005 - 2010 in northeast China (unpublished).

The study area is located in northeast China at the Chinese and Russian border (Figure 1). The spatial extent is between 42°N - 55.5°N and 115.5°E - 135.6°E with an approximated size of about 2.8 million km^2 . The dominant land cover is needle-leaf forest in the north of the study area, whereas in the south of the study area big patches of agricultural land cover are dominating. The terrain height is also highly diverse within the study area (Figure 1). In the center of the study area the terrain is flat with heights between 0 - 600 m, whereas in the west, north and east of the study area shows a hilly terrain with heights ranging between 600 - 1,800 m. Namely known mountain ranges are the *Altai Mountains* (west), *Greater Khingan* (north) and *Changbai Mountains* (east).

3. METHODS

'CCI Landcover' products were used in both approaches ('Mixed Forest Pixel' / 'Pure Forest Pixel') while all other products were only utilized in the 'Pure Pixel Analysis' (see Figure 2). Both approaches were combined into one workflow to show up differences while simultaneously reduce redundancy.

Figure 2. Workflow for 'pure pixel analysis' and 'mixed pixel analysis'

Table 2. Reclassification key of 'CCI Land cover'

Product	CCI LC class ID	Reclassification	Reference
CCI LC 2005 & 2010	50, 60-62, 70-72, 80-82, 90	Forest	[11]
	120, 121, 122	Shrub	
	130	Grass	
	10-12, 20	Crop	

3.1. 'Mixed forest pixel' analysis

In this analysis we compared GSV distributions of BIOMASAR pixels containing a mixture of forest and other classes related to vegetation (shrub, grass, crop). The goal was to investigate influences of vegetation related classes in combination with forest regarding GSV derivation in C-band, which is used in the BIOMASAR algorithm [5]. Most remote sensing products covering a large area feature a spatial resolution in hundreds of meters and introduce scale problems, no matter if they show land cover information, biomass estimation or other environmental information. The BIOMASAR products feature a spatial resolution of 1 km. Hence, they are clearly affected by scale problems (e.g. varying land cover within each pixel) when providing one GSV value over 1 km².

As we were not interested in specific forest classes, the first step was to conduct a reclassification of all classes related to forest into a class named 'Forest'. We also reclassified CCI LC classes which were used for the 'mixed forest pixel' classes, namely "Shrub", "Crop" and "Grass" (Table 2). Basically, we aggregated all related subclasses to one super class containing "Shrub", "Crop" or "Grass", respectively. Other classes were left default.

To show influences on GSV derivation with a varying percentage of non-forest classes, BIOMASAR pixels were classified according to their Forest/Non-Forest class percentage. We used quantiles (see Figure 2) to classify

respective forest/non-forest percentages, ending up with four mixed-class types: 0%-25% * x, 25%-50% * x, 50%-75% * x, 75%-100% * x, with 'x' being either 'Shrub', 'Grass' or 'Crop' and 75%-100%, 50%-75%, 25%-50%, 0%-25% representing 'Forest', respectively. BIOMASAR pixels matching one of the 16 classes were extracted and its GSV values visualized using boxplots for each year.

3.2. 'Pure forest pixel' analysis

This analysis aims to serve as a cross-validation of the BIOMASAR maps using global land cover products. Since the BIOMASAR products are only valid for forest areas, we focused on selecting pure forest pixels within the BIOMASAR products to compare its GSV for 2005 and 2010, respectively. While the BIOMASAR algorithm after [5] utilizes MODIS VCF to distinguish between Forest/Non-Forest, our approach takes three global land cover products as well as one forest/non-forest map into account (see Figure 2). By combining information of four products, classification errors introduced by land cover products get minimized.

First, a zonal analysis of land cover class distribution within BIOMASAR pixels was conducted. Only pixels which showed a predominant classification of 'Forest' in all products (CCI LC, MODIS LC, GlobelLand30, PALSAR Forest/Non-forest) in both years were selected (see Table 3). However, this temporary selection still includes forest pixels mixed with other land cover. To account for this, we computed the relative area of each land cover class within each BIOMASAR pixel using CCI LC and selected only pixels with an *relative area of class 'Forest' = 100%* for both years (2005 and 2010). This leaves us with 342.838 (out of 2.8 x 10⁶) BIOMASAR pixels in 2005 and 2010 which are completely covered by forest according to our approach.

Table 3. Reclassification key 'Pure Pixel Analysis'

Product	LC class ID	Reclass.	Reference
CCI LC 2005 & 2010	50, 60-62, 70-72, 80-82, 90	Forest	[11]
MODIS LC 2005-2010	1, 2, 3, 4, 5		[12]
GlobeLand 2010	30		[13]

GSV distribution analysis

The following analysis step depends on Figure 5 which shows the GSV distribution of 'pure forest pixels' in 2005 and 2010.

Some pixels show a high difference in GSV from 2005-2010 or 2010-2005, meaning there was quite some change going on. The change value of "> 100 m³/ha" has no statistical background and was chosen according to the overall distribution of the data values with respect to practical experience. By this we mean that a GSV change of 100 m³/ha in 5 years is most often influenced by mankind

and not only nature. To investigate this drop/increase, we looked on possible influences on GSV derivation when using the BIOMASAR algorithm.

Radar scenes are usually influenced by slope (e.g. [18]). Therefore slope statistics within the respective pixels showing a high GSV difference throughout the years were investigated.

As the BIOMASAR algorithm relies on hypertemporal ASAR stacks, the number of scenes has a big influence on the robustness of each derived GSV value [5]. To account for this, we checked the number of ASAR scenes for each year for the respective change pixels. To show differences across the map and between pixels with a differing number of scenes, groups with a range of ten scenes were set up (e.g. 10-19, 20-29, 30-39 etc.).

3.3. 'Plausibility Check' of the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010

The BIOMASAR algorithm was only validated for forest areas. Therefore, the 'Plausibility Check' utilized only 'pure forest pixels' carried out within the 'Pure Pixel Analysis' (subsection 3.2). Furthermore the prerequisite of being classified as a "Pure Forest Pixel" for both years 2005 and 2010 was set. To reduce noise within the data and ensure to account for real GSV changes, only percentual GSV changes $\geq 35\%$ between 2005-2010 were included. This threshold relies on the relative RMSE of around 35% of the BIOMASAR algorithm in similar biomes [5]. Trends throughout the years were calculated for MODIS NDVI and MODIS VCF returning a True/False response whether the increase or decrease of the BIOMASAR GSV change map was reasonable according to the observed vegetation trends (see Figure 3). Moreover pixel that showed a fire activity based on both fire products (MODIS Burned Area & Landsat based Burned Area) during that time were marked as reasonable GSV decrease, whereas no fire activity indicated a reasonable GSV increase. All these information were combined to create a plausibility map for increasing and decreasing GSV values of the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010.

4. RESULTS

4.1. 'Mixed forest pixel' analysis

Mixed pixel class distributions for 2005 and 2010 show a varying number of pixels for each class ranging from $N = 2317$ (Forest-Shrub 75-100% 2010) up to $N = 83263$ (Forest-Shrub 0-25% 2005)(see Figure 4). This has to be kept in mind when looking at each class although the smallest group still contains a sufficient number of observations. Boxplots show the distribution statistics of each

Figure 3. Workflow for 'plausibility check'

class (25% quantile, 50% quantile (= median), 75% quantile) while the double sided curves refer to violin plots which show observation densities of each observed value, similar to a histogram view of the distribution.

Regarding classes "Forest-Crop" and "Forest-Grass" for 2005 and 2010, a decrease in GSV with an increase of the respective mixed-pixel class can be observed. Class distributions of these classes show a gaussian shape with some positive outliers. The "Forest-Shrub" classes for 2005 and 2010 show an inconsistent behaviour with an increase of the mixed-pixel class (here "Shrub"). The median of the first three classes (0-25%, 25-50% and 50-75%) stays roughly the same and a decrease of GSV (median) can only be observed for class "Forest-Shrub 75-100%" for both years 2005 and 2010. Furthermore, "Forest-Shrub" classes show a bimodality in their class distributions. With a higher percentage of class "Shrub" within the "Forest-Shrub" classes for both years 2005 and 2010, the bimodality shape becomes more evident.

4.2. 'Pure forest pixel' analysis

GSV values of "Pure Forest Pixel" retrieved from the BIOMASAR algorithm show, on average, a decrease in GSV from 2005 to 2010 by a factor of 0.78 including a RMSE of 25,70 m³/ha and an explained variance of 79% by the regression model shown. Red points represent all "Pure Forest Pixel" pairs showing a difference in GSV > 100 between the years, either 2005 $>$ 2010 or 2005 $<$ 2010 ($N = 1235$). Black points show pairs with a GSV difference smaller than 100 throughout the years with a sample size of 398.049 (2.800.000 pixels total). In summary, 399.284 pixels were detected as "Pure Forest Pixel" according to our approach explained in subsection 3.2.

Figure 4. 'Mixed Pixel Analysis' results for classes "Forest-Crop", "Forest-Grass", "Forest-Shrub". Classes are grouped in quantiles according to their "Forest-mixed class" combination. E.g.: Forest-Crop 2005 (0-25% Crop) refers to pixels containing 0-25% Crop and 75-100% Forest according to CCI LC

Regarding the slope analysis of the pixel pairs showing a GSV difference > 100 , blue points mark the location of such pairs (see Figure 6). On the left map, pairs showing a smaller value in 2005 than in 2010 are colored green while pixels having a larger value in 2005 than in 2010 are colored red. The right map shows a zoomed view on the main concentration of pairs showing a high difference throughout the years including the slope values displayed in the background. Slope values range from $0-20^\circ$ in steps of 5° . To investigate a possible influence of processed ASAR scenes per pixel on GSV derivation by the BIOMASAR algorithm, we looked at the spatial distribution of pixels showing a low number of available scenes (overall minimum: 10 scenes) and the extracted pairs showing a GSV difference. Figure 8 shows the

spatial distribution of pixels featuring a low number of scenes (10-29) for the year 2005 (mean 2005 = 101.37, mean 2010 = 122.67). Exploring further, a statistical analysis of all pixels was carried out based on the 'number of scenes' for 2005 and 2010. We assumed 2005 to be the problematic year as the mean number of scenes was clearly lower than in 2010 for all pixels (see Figure 7). With an increase in the number of scenes, RMSE decreases, r^2 increases and the maximum difference pair value for each group decreases (Figure 7 plot down right) from a GSV difference of roughly 165 (10-19 scenes) to a GSV difference of around 110 m³/ha.

Figure 5. GSV distribution of "Pure Forest Pixels" of the BIOMASAR maps for 2005 and 2010

Figure 6. Slope statistics and spatial distribution of BIOMASAR "Pure Forest Pixels" with a GSV difference > 100 for 2005-2010 or 2010-2005.pdf

Figure 7. Analysis of GSV values 2005 & 2010 depending on the number of used ASAR scenes for the year 2005

4.3. 'Plausibility Check' of the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010

The plausibility check of the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010 shows distinct patches of plausible GSV changes (agreement with more than one product) along the Chinese and Russian border, especially in the north, northeast and east of the study area (Figure 9). In total 19,309 pixels showed increasing GSV values based on the BIOMASAR GSV change map for 2005 to 2010 and 10,614 pixel showed a decrease of GSV (Table 4).

For the increasing GSV values all pixels were reasonable based on at least one other used remote sensing product. 2,126 decreasing BIOMASAR GSV pixel on the other hand were not explained by any other remote sensing product. Noticeable are two patches in the center of the study area of decreasing pixels which were not explained by other products. Moreover some scattered decreasing change pixel did not show an agreement in the east and north of the study area, whereas in the northeast mostly all decreasing BIOMASAR GSV pixel were explained by at least one other product.

Figure 8. BIOMASAR pixels with number of ASAR scenes ranging from 10-29 for the year 2005 and pixels with GSV Difference > 100 for 2005 - 2010

Figure 9. Agreement map of increasing (l) and decreasing (r) BIOMASAR GSV change pixel from 2005 - 2010 based on cross-comparison with various existing remote sensing products

Table 4. Areal statistics of the plausibility check of the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010

Agreement with	Increase		Decrease		Increase & Decrease	
	Number of pixel	Area [%]	Number of pixel	Area [%]	Number of pixel	Area [%]
0 products	0	0	2,126	20.03	2,126	7.10
1 product	79	0.41	5,840	55.02	5,919	19.78
2 products	4,285	22.19	2,546	23.99	6,831	22.83
3 products	10,362	53.66	102	0.96	10,464	34.97
4 products	4,583	23.74	0	0	4,583	15.32
Total	19,309	100	10,614	100	29,923	100

Overall only 2,126 of the 1km GSV change pixel (increase & decrease) did not show an agreement with any of the other used remote sensing products, which is only 7.1 % of all GSV change pixel (Table 4). In return 27,797 (92,9%) GSV change pixel of all detected valid changes are reasonable based on at least one other used remote sensing product (Table 4).

5. FOREST-DRAGON GEOPORTAL

The objective of the *Forest Dragon Geoport* is to present the results of the Forest-DRAGON projects 1-3 and the earth observation products used within the analyses. The *Forest-DRAGON Geoport* is based on the *ArcOnline WebMapping* application including a cloud-storage system. Datasets are uploaded as .kml files (Figure 10). This way, a quick site response is achieved in combination with low memory storage requirements.

Note: During the time of paper publication, an unresolved problem with .kml data occupying large areas existed. In response to that, the ArcOnline support assures updates on a regular base, which should eliminate this problem in the near future. Generally, the *Forest-DRAGON Geoport* offers user-friendly site navigation, a fresh design and can be easily adopted to new data.

6. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper the Forest DRAGON 3 final results of the European partners have been presented.

Within the 'Mixed Pixel Analysis' an expected decrease for "Forest-Crop" and "Forest-Grass" were observed while class "Forest-Shrub" showed an expected confusion (i.e. high variance within each "Forest-Shrub" class distribution) including an unresolved bimodality becoming stronger as shrub-percentage increases. Since this second mode appears at a GSV of around 200 m³/ha, this case should be further investigated in future studies. Overall, this investigation can be seen as cross-validation for both BIOMASAR and CCI LC products with a good agreement compared to a priori analysis outcome expectations.

Addressing the 'Pure Pixel Analysis', interesting patterns of BIOMASAR pixels showing high differences

Figure 10. Simplified flow chart of the Forest-DRAGON Geoport structure

in GSV between the years 2005 - 2010 were investigated. It was found to be mostly related to the available number of ASAR scenes used within the BIOMASAR algorithm where especially in 2005 a low number of scenes was detected for the specific change pixels. Slope might also have an effect on the robustness of each pixel's GSV retrieval due to its influence on radar images. Due to the combination of different products (BIOMASAR, CCI LC, MODIS LC, PALSAR Forest/Non-Forest, Globeland), topographic influences (e.g. terrain) and scale effects within the products, it is not possible to ascribe error sources back to a specific product in this work.

During the 'Plausibility Check' of the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010 with the help of various existing remote sensing products all valid increasing GSV change pixel showed a reasonable behaviour with at least one other product. However clustered and some scattered decreasing GSV change pixel (2,126 pxl; 20.03%) in the northwest, east and southeast of the study area showed an inconsistency. Overall only 7.10% (2,126 pxl) of all valid GSV change pixel did not have a plausible behaviour, whereas in return 92.9% (27,797 pxl) showed an agreement with at least one other tested remote sensing product. Therefore the BIOMASAR GSV change map of 2005 - 2010 showed an overall good accuracy during this cross-comparison.

In DRAGON 4 information gathered by images from various Sentinel satellites sets a new possibility to investigate Biomass changes even more closely by having access to images with higher temporal- and spatial resolution than in DRAGON 3. These images can be used to create a BIOMASAR map for the year 2015 and compare its quality with older BIOMASAR maps from 2005 and 2010.

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